

Attitude towards Information Technology among the Senior Secondary School Teachers

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Abstract

The key indicator of a teacher's competence to employ technology for teaching is their attitude towards it. A teacher's attitude towards information technology also has an impact on the quality of the work they produce. Thus, this study aimed to explore the level of senior secondary teacher's attitude towards information technology (IT) and their attitude towards information technology (IT) with respect to Gender variable. This study was carried out by using descriptive survey method. The study's sample comprised of 75 senior secondary school teachers from the East District of Sikkim. The study's findings highlighted the percentage of teachers in different levels of attitudes towards information technology, as well as the difference in the mean attitude score between male and female teachers towards information technology.

Keywords: Information Technology, Sr. Secondary, School Teachers.

Introduction

Information technology (IT), which covers the processes of information gathering, creation, processing, and storage, as well as communicating with others, is the science that deals with many sorts of information. In this context, Ray (2012) stated that "Information technology is a recent and comprehensive term, which describes the whole range of processes for generation, storage, transmission, retrieval and processing of information" (p.398). For the development of the effectiveness of teaching-learning process, information technology must be used. In this regard, Nasrin and Islahi (2012) stated that in order to encourage a more positive attitude toward integrating technologies in the teaching-learning process, it is crucial to evaluate attitude of teachers toward using information technology. This is because the successful implementation of information technology always depends on teachers' willingness and attitudes toward using it.

The findings of some studies revealed that the significant difference was there in teachers' attitude towards using information technology with respect to gender variable (Albert, 2015) and female teachers showed more attitudes towards information and communication technology (ICT) as compared to male teachers (Yadav, 2015). Whereas the findings of some other studies revealed no significant difference between male and female teachers in their attitude towards information technology (Kumar, 2017; Mwila, 2018; Sehjal, 2021). Sikkim is the place where all the schools are provided various resources related to technology for teaching learning process. Therefore, the researcher intended to do this study to project the present status of school teachers teaching in senior secondary level in East District of Sikkim on attitude towards information technology.

Objectives

- i. To study the level of attitude towards information technology among the senior secondary school teachers.
- ii. To study the attitude towards information technology among the senior secondary school teachers in relation to Gender variable.

Hypothesis

H₀₁ There is no significant difference between male and female senior secondary school teachers in attitude towards information technology.

Research Method and Procedures

This study was carried out by using descriptive survey method which is relevant and justified. In the present study the sample was drawn from the teachers teaching in class XI and XII of senior secondary schools situated in East districts of Sikkim State. 75 teachers teaching in class XI and XII were the sample of this study. For sample selection, stratified random sampling technique was employed. To collect the requisite data for present study the investigator used the following tool: 'Attitude Scale towards Information Technology for Teachers' developed by Nasrin and Islahi (2012). Data analysis was done using both descriptive and inferential statistics.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Teachers were categorised under different levels of attitude towards using information technology.

Table 1
Levels of Teacher's attitude towards Information Technology

Levels of attitude for Information Technology	No of teachers	% of teachers
Extremely Favourable Attitude	0	0
Highly Favourable Attitude	0	0
Positively Favourable Attitude	58	77.33
Moderate Favourable Attitude	17	22.67
Unfavourable Attitude	0	0
Highly Unfavourable Attitude	0	0
Extremely Unfavourable Attitude	0	0
Total	75	100

The above table no. 1 revealed that 22.67% of senior secondary school teachers had Moderate Favourable Attitude and 77.33 % of teachers had Positively Favourable Attitude towards information technology. No teachers were there in any other categories i.e., Extremely Favourable Attitude, Highly Favourable Attitude, Unfavourable Attitude, Highly Unfavourable Attitude and Extremely Unfavourable Attitude. Therefore, it can be said that most of the senior secondary school teachers had positively favourable attitude towards information technology.

To test H₀₁ and to determine whether there was a difference in the mean scores of male and female senior secondary school teachers on their attitudes toward information technology the test of significance i.e., *t* test was employed and the result is shown in the following table no 2.

Table 2
Significance of Difference in Mean Scores on Attitude Towards Information Technology
between Male and Female Senior Secondary School Teachers

Attitude towards Information Technology	Male (32)		Female (43)		<i>t</i> (73)	<i>p</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
	110.75	10.09	114.53	11.91	1.45	.151

The results of the independent sample two-tailed *t*-test indicated $t(73) = 1.45, p = > .05$. Thus, the difference was not found to be significant and hence the null hypothesis H₀₁ was failed to be rejected.

Therefore, it could be concluded that no significant difference was there between male and female senior secondary school teachers in their attitude towards information technology.

Conclusion

The present study revealed teachers' attitude toward information technology since this is an important aspect that indicates teachers' readiness to use information technology for teaching purposes, and the excellence of a teacher's work is influenced by the attitude they possess towards information technology. The following general inferences can be made in light of the study's major findings: most of the senior secondary school teachers have positively favourable attitude towards information technology and there exists no significant difference between the male and female senior secondary school teachers in their attitude towards information technology. With the purpose of fostering extremely favourable attitude toward information technology among pre-service and in-service teachers, the current study will assist principals, administrators, policy makers, and trainers in developing more appropriate and successful teacher training frameworks. This study may help educationist, researchers, and teachers to enhance the standard of teaching-learning process which is primarily dependent on the degree to which teachers possess knowledge about information technology and their ability to use it in the classroom.

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